

MESOSTRUCTURE-INFORMED NUMERICAL MODELLING OF POST-CONSOLIDATION ARCHITECTURE IN ADVANCED PLACED PLY LAMINATES

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Keywords: Automated Fibre Placement, Architected Materials, X-ray Computed Tomography, Finite Element Modelling

ABSTRACT

With the advent of advanced composite additive manufacturing techniques such as Automated Fibre Placement, enhanced control over the layup architectures of composite laminates has become feasible. One notable design opportunity arising from this advancement is the Advanced Placed Ply (AP-Ply) strategy which offers a promising possibility to substantially enhance delamination resistance and damage tolerance in composite laminates. As these architectures involve tows traversing across different laminate plies, conventional ply-wise modelling strategies are insufficient for accurately predicting their mechanical behaviour. A comprehensive understanding of their internal architecture, along with the effective translation of these structural characteristics into numerical models, is therefore imperative. To this end, the present work focuses on the detailed morphological characterisation of AP-Ply laminates and the subsequent development of morphology-informed numerical models. By overcoming the limitations of existing characterisation studies, this approach advances the mechanistic insight into AP-Ply architectures and simultaneously lays the groundwork for rapid and scalable performance prediction of numerous such configurations made possible through tow-level layup customisation.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the growing sophistication in composites manufacturing, there has been a search for novel design strategies that can enhance the critical mechanical properties of composite laminates. Such novel design strategies should be adaptable with advanced manufacturing methods, like Automated Fibre Placement (AFP), to enable their effective integration into current manufacturing practices and support scalable adoption. Among these, Advanced Placed Ply (AP-Ply) architectures present a promising approach to significantly improve delamination resistance and damage tolerance in composite laminates [1,2]. Numerous studies have explored the damage tolerance of these architectures through compression-after-impact (CAI) tests, reporting configuration-dependent enhancements of 5–26% relative to conventional unidirectional composites [2–6]. This is achieved by the strategic modification of the tow placement sequence, to create architectures akin to the textile laminates. The tow drop features formed by interweaving the tows from one ply to adjacent plies act as effective crack arrestors to resist delamination propagation.

The AP-Ply layup strategy strategically skips a defined number of adjacent tows during the initial deposition passes along a specific fibre orientation. Subsequent passes, executed in alternate fibre directions, are then used to populate these intentionally left gaps, resulting in a laminate with consistent overall thickness. An example of AP-Ply architecture employing a single tow skipping is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Buildup of the most straightforward AP-Ply Pattern [0,90].

Altering the sequence of tow placement in AP-Ply laminates facilitates the creation of varied meso-architectures, each with distinct mechanical characteristics. However, determining the optimal configuration for a specific application through trial-and-error methods is resource-intensive and time-consuming. This highlights the necessity for a robust computational framework capable of accurately predicting both mechanical responses and failure mechanisms in such complex architectures.

Conventional ply-level modelling approaches are inadequate for representing AP-Ply laminates, as these architectures feature inter-ply tow transversal. To address this, several modelling strategies have emerged. Li et al. [7] developed a tow-wise modelling (TWM) methodology, which showed good agreement in predicting short beam strength [8], though it underperformed in simulating damage propagation under low-velocity impact [5]. Alternatively, Kok et al. [9] proposed a unit-cell-based model that homogenised undulation zones into simplified box-like elements. While this approach produced satisfactory results for quasi-static and dynamic tensile simulations [9,10], it also fell short in accurately predicting impact-induced damage [6].

These inconsistencies stem from oversimplifications in the representation of meso-scale features. Existing models often approximate tow cross-sections as idealised rectangles and address tow junctions using separation-based contact interactions or homogenisation techniques [7,9], rather than explicitly modelling the tapering of tows near the edges. Realistic simulation of deformation and damage progression at the tow level requires a detailed geometrical description of the mesoscale architecture, particularly the "tow drops", which are distinct geometric features formed where tows shift between plies.

Two principal domains have addressed meso-structural characterisation of tow drops. The first focuses on fibre waviness induced by defects such as gaps or overlaps during the layup process, which can degrade in-plane performance by up to 45% [11–13]. Here, parameters like undulation amplitude, wavelength, and angle are commonly extracted from optical micrographs, with sinusoidal representations often used to approximate tow trajectories [14–17]. However, these investigations primarily deal with isolated features and do not reflect the periodicity and complexity of patterned AP-Ply designs.

The second area relates to textile composites, where post-consolidation fibre geometry has been extensively studied using various characterisation techniques, particularly X-ray computed tomography (CT) [18–20]. Various segmentation strategies have been introduced to identify individual tow morphology, including automated approaches based on structure tensor analysis of greyscale intensity gradients [21,22]. However, challenges persist in resolving tow structures at lower voxel resolutions, that are required to capture large-scale architectural patterns, due to low phase contrast in carbon fibre-reinforced polymers (CFRPs). Even advanced techniques such as structure tensor filtering or contour stitching struggle to delineate tow boundaries when in-plane intensity gradients are weak.

This work presents the first comprehensive attempt to parametrically evaluate the post-consolidation tow morphology in AP-ply laminates using a combination of multiple characterisation techniques. High-resolution microscopic imaging is employed to capture out-of-plane undulation characteristics, while low-resolution CT scans with large scanning windows enable 3D visualisation of the periodic tow structure. A novel through-thickness morphological gradient based approach is introduced which leverages directional differences in X-ray attenuation caused by fibre orientation to enhance the visibility of low-contrast features, enabling more effective interpretation of internal geometry in CFRPs. The extracted morphological parameters are then incorporated into finite element simulations of tensile behaviour, with the numerical predictions validated against experimental results from corresponding AFP-fabricated specimens.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Manufacturing

Three distinct AP-Ply laminate configurations with $[0/90]$ design were fabricated (as shown in Figure 1), each differing in the spacing between adjacent tows. The first configuration followed the standard AP-Ply layup, incorporating a single tow gap that was subsequently filled during later passes in the same orientation. In contrast, the second and third configurations introduced additional inter-tow gaps measuring 40% and 80% of the tow width respectively, which resulted in final inter-tow gaps of 20% and 40% of the tow width after all passes were completed.

Carbon fibre epoxy prepreg tapes (HTS45E23/E-752-LT) by Park Aerospace, were used for the layup. Each tape measured 6.35 mm in width and 0.19 mm in thickness. The layup process was carried out using an AFP machine developed by Trelleborg Sealing Solutions® located at the University of New South Wales. For each configuration, ten AP-Ply style plies were deposited to form square panels measuring 300 mm \times 300 mm. Curing was performed in an ASC autoclave at 177°C and 6.2 bar, following the supplier's recommended protocol.

Prior to consolidation, surface irregularities were evident across all panels. These were caused either by out-of-plane waviness in the no-gap configuration or by the presence of inter-tow gaps in the gapped variants. However, post-consolidation, all laminates exhibited smooth and uniform surfaces. This can be attributed to tow spreading, which not only filled the gaps but also led to a reduction in overall thickness for the gapped panels. Final thicknesses were measured at 2.55 mm and 2.2 mm for the 20% and 40% gap configurations, respectively. In contrast, the baseline and 0% gap panels retained a thickness of 3 mm, consistent with the material's standard specification. Figure 2 illustrates the layup progression for the 40% gap configuration.

Figure 2: Hot gas torch-based AFP machine at UNSW Sydney. The right side of the figure presents a robot layup sequence during the fabrication of 40% gap AP-Ply configuration.

2.2 Optical Microscopy

The undulation patterns were analysed using optical microscopy to examine the internal structure of the laminates. For each configuration, small specimens were extracted along the midline of the undulating tows. Microscopic imaging was performed using a DSX510 optical microscope operating at 10 \times magnification. The boundaries of the undulating tows were extracted through digital image processing of the obtained high-resolution optical micrographs. A sine wave-like curve emerged when the manually traced coordinates were plotted on the X-Y axis. This curve was then fitted to a sine

function to characterise the undulation. By calculating the maximum slope of the fitted curve, the out-of-plane undulation angle was estimated. Figure 3 graphically illustrates the methodology described above.

Figure 3: Characterisation methodology for optical microscopy method.

2.3 X-Ray CT scanning

To complement the 2D insights from optical microscopy, a three-dimensional understanding of the laminate morphology was obtained through X-ray computed tomography (CT). Using a HeliScan™ micro-CT system (Mark I), samples from each configuration measuring 44 mm x 35 mm were scanned. A voxel resolution of 29.44 μm was selected, balancing the need to capture at least twice the representative unit cell (RUC) size with sufficient detail to resolve the sinusoidal tow undulations.

Scans were conducted along a circular trajectory at 60 kV and 105 μA , with a 1 mm aluminium filter, and the rotation axis aligned parallel to the warp (1st pass) tows. This setup ensured that the warp fibres remained perpendicular to the X-ray beam throughout the scan, while the weft fibres rotated from perpendicular to parallel orientations. Due to their alignment with the X-ray beam during scanning, the weft fibres experienced increased attenuation, primarily caused by small-angle scattering. This resulted in slightly higher intensity values for such voxels. To verify that this contrast was directionally dependent, the laminate (20% gap configuration) was rotated so that the weft fibres remained perpendicular to the beam throughout the scan. Under this new orientation, the warp fibres exhibited increased intensity, confirming the influence of fibre orientation on X-ray attenuation.

Because the inter-ply spacing was much smaller than the voxel resolution and no universal threshold could reliably distinguish warp from weft tows, conventional segmentation techniques proved ineffective. To overcome these limitations, signal processing-based algorithms were developed to identify individual tows within the bulk laminate structure.

Prominent intensity peaks, attributed to the asymmetrical scanning setup, were observed in the through-thickness intensity profiles and corresponded to the weft tows. These peaks were used to precisely map the geometry of the weft tows. As demonstrated in the 20% gap configuration, rotating the CT scan setup proves to be an effective approach for characterising the geometry of warp tows.

To detect the most prominent peaks in the intensity data, the `find_peaks` function in Python was applied, using a minimum spacing parameter based on ply thickness. However, due to sub-peak

detection or missing prominent peaks, the number of detected peaks sometimes differed from the actual number of weft plies. To correct these inconsistencies, a sequence correction algorithm was introduced. This method replaced inaccurate peak sets, those with incorrect lengths, with corrected ones inferred from adjacent regions where the peak count matched the expected ply number. Figure 4 presents the flow chart for the above-described characterisation methodology.

Figure 4: Characterisation methodology for individual tow segmentation using CT-scan data.

2.4 Tensile testing

Following ASTM D3039, tensile tests were conducted to evaluate the static mechanical performance of the fabricated laminates. Using a water-cooled diamond saw, five specimens per configuration were sectioned to 35.56 mm × 254 mm, with their length aligned along the warp direction. To mitigate fibre damage at the grips, 82 mm-long glass fibre tabs were bonded to both ends using epoxy resin. Testing was performed on an Instron 3369 machine, equipped with hydraulic grips to maintain secure clamping. A constant displacement rate of 2 mm/min was applied throughout the test. Strain measurement was achieved using unidirectional linear gauges placed on the underside of each specimen, directly above a non-undulating warp tow.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

To preserve key architectural features while maintaining computational efficiency, several geometric simplifications were introduced in the AP-Ply laminate models:

1. Instead of manually modelling the unique undulation angle for each tow, the average undulation angle derived from microscopy data, was applied uniformly across all tows in both directions.
2. The sinusoidal out-of-plane tow paths were idealised as trapezoidal trajectories. This assumption, commonly adopted in textile composite modelling improves mesh conformity and eliminates voids, thereby enhancing computational performance.
3. A trapezoidal cross-section was assigned to each tow, to capture the tapering at tow edges. This choice complements the trapezoidal undulation profile and further facilitates the generation of a conformal mesh.

Figure 5 illustrates the representative geometric models constructed using these assumptions.

Figure 5: Representative geometry of the undulating tow along with longitudinal and transverse cross sections views.

To predict failure initiation in composite laminates, 3D Hashin criterion is employed due to its ability to differentiate between fibre and matrix damage under both tensile and compressive loads [23]. This extended formulation consists of four distinct sub-criteria, each addressing a specific failure mode.

Fibre tension failure:

$$F_{ft} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

Fibre compression failure:

$$F_{fc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

Matrix tension failure:

$$F_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_{23}^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

Matrix compression failure:

$$F_{mc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_c} \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 - 1 \right] + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_{23}^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

Post-failure behaviour in composite laminates is heavily influenced by how damage evolves across different failure modes. Although various softening laws, like linear, exponential, or sigmoidal, have been proposed [9,24], the bilinear softening model offers the most accurate representation of tensile stress-strain response along the fibre direction [24,25] and hence been used to simulate fibre tensile damage evolution in this work. Damage evolution for the remaining failure modes is modelled through linear softening model.

To simulate inter-tow interactions, built-in contact algorithms in ABAQUS were used. Cohesive surfaces governed by a linear traction-separation law captured interlaminar behaviour, with delamination strength defining the peak traction. Normal and tangential contact forces were handled using ABAQUS' general contact algorithm, where a hard contact condition was applied to prevent ply interpenetration. The material parameters for the prepreg tapes (HTS45E23/E-752-LT) were utilised according to the specifications outlined in previous studies [8,26,27].

Displacement-controlled boundary conditions were imposed at one end of the laminate, while the opposite end was fully constrained in ABAQUS Explicit. A smooth ramp function was used to gradually increase displacement to reduce dynamic effects from sudden loading.

Mesh sensitivity analysis guided the selection of a 0.5 mm mesh size, ensuring reliable results without excessive computational cost. Given the trapezoidal tow geometry, wedge elements (C3D6) were employed to maintain uniform meshing. Element deletion was triggered when the fibre damage factor exceeded 1, indicating complete stiffness degradation in the fibre direction.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Optical Microscopy

To quantify tow undulation, edge coordinates from the fifth ply were extracted and fitted to a sine function, enabling derivation of undulation parameters for each laminate configuration. While the 0% gap configuration exhibited a near-perfect sinusoidal trajectory, and the 20% gap case followed a similar pattern, the 40% gap configuration deviated significantly. This disruption was caused by ply slippage, which introduced irregular overlaps and gaps at tow junctions, resulting in alternating steep and shallow undulation slopes.

Figure 6 reports the undulation angles along with associated uncertainties. In both the 0% and 20% gap cases, the weft direction exhibited higher undulation angles than the warp. However, the 20% gap configuration showed reduced undulation angles overall, attributed to thinner tows and increased spacing between them.

Figure 6: Microscopy derived undulation angle for each AP-Ply configuration in both warp and weft direction. Error bars represent standard deviation.

4.2 X-Ray CT scanning

To locate the mid-planes of warp and weft tows, morphological gradients along the thickness direction were analysed. After filtering, the 3D geometry and mid-line trajectory of the same ply are visualised in Figure 7. The undulating tows in the 0% case closely follow sinusoidal path, where 20% gap case showed considerable deviation. This regularity breaks down further in the 40% gap configuration, where the trajectory shows altering pattern mirroring microscopy observations.

Doubly curved mid-planes of the weft tows at the crest zones were a unique morphology characteristic observed in 3D analysis. These curvatures are due to their location directly beneath the undulations of the warp tows. In contrast, peak regions above straight tows show no such curvature. However, CT scan analysis consistently reported angles 15–20% lower than microscopic observations for various directions and configurations. This discrepancy stems from the limited resolution of CT scans, where undulation heights are only 4–5 times the voxel size.

Still, CT-based measurements correctly captured key trends such as higher weft undulation angles in the 0% gap case than the warp angles and a general reduction in angle for the 20% gap configuration. While CT offers valuable 3D visualisation, its quantitative accuracy remains resolution-dependent.

Figure 7: Visualisation of the undulating tows in each AP-ply configuration and their corresponding out-of-plane trajectory (with fitted sine-curve).

4.3 Tensile performance

The tensile response of AP-Ply laminates was simulated using the morphologically-informed model described in Section 3. Figure 8 compares the simulated tensile behaviour for each configuration with the experimentally observed response. Given the high degree of manufacturing inconsistencies observed in 40% gap laminate, this configuration was excluded from the FEA analysis. Table 1 presents a summarized comparison of the numerical and experimental strength values. Compared to conventional models [8,9], this approach significantly improves predictive accuracy.

Minor under-prediction of strength was observed across simulations, specifically for 0% gap configuration. This can be attributed to the sharp geometric transitions in the modelled laminate, which differ from the smoother contours found in actual specimens. Despite experimental results showing nearly identical strength, the simulation predicted slightly higher values for the 20% gap configuration than the 0% gap case. This discrepancy stems from minor defects found during characterisation of the 20% gap samples, which were not included in the model.

The numerical model effectively captured both the onset and evolution of tensile failure mechanisms. Owing to the lower strain-to-failure threshold in the matrix compared to the fibres, matrix tensile damage initiated early in the transverse tows. This damage mode progressively intensified, ultimately leading to complete matrix failure and a significant reduction in transverse stiffness within the failed tows much before fibre failure occurred.

Figure 8: Stress-strain response obtained through simulation for each configuration.

Configuration	Strength, MPa (CV%)	Simulated Strength, MPa	Error (%)
XP	1087.92 (2.00%)	1082.08	-0.54%
0% Gap	1055.09 (2.60%)	997.38	-5.47%
20% Gap	1032.75 (2.70%)	1012.67	-1.94%

Table 1: Comparison of experimental and simulated tensile strength.

Figure 9 shows the stress field maps which identifies the stress concentration sites in longitudinal tows, particularly near nodes where transverse tows taper. These regions are formed by the intersection of flat and sloped surfaces which creates sharp edges that triggered fibre failure. Once initiated, failure propagated rapidly due to low fracture toughness in the fibre direction. Crack fronts in longitudinal tows develop in transverse direction, which is coherent with post-failure inspection of the tested samples.

Figure 9: a) Stress distribution field showing principal stress in fibre direction when the fibre failure initiates; b) Fibre tensile damage initiation sites in longitudinal tow.

9 CONCLUSIONS

This study utilises detailed morphological characterisation of AP-Ply laminates to develop a high-fidelity finite element model capable of accurately predicting their tensile behaviour. Three distinct AP-

Ply architectures were fabricated using a hot-gas torch-based Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) system. While the layup process initially produced highly uneven surfaces, the developed protrusions or gaps were eliminated post-curing, primarily due to tow spreading. Internal geometries for these laminates were characterised using optical microscopy and X-ray computed tomography (CT), and the extracted meso-structural data were parameterised to construct representative geometries for numerical modelling.

Given the minimal inter-ply spacing after consolidation and the limited resolution of CT scans, conventional segmentation techniques proved inadequate. To address this, novel segmentation algorithms were developed to reliably isolate individual tows.

Notably, AP-Ply laminates maintained strength and stiffness performance close to baseline laminates, despite the presence of fibre undulations. This reinforces their suitability as replacements for conventional non-woven architectures, with the added benefit of enhanced toughness.

The morphologically informed numerical framework developed in this work demonstrated strong predictive capability, estimating tensile strength within a 6% margin of experimental results. Furthermore, the model successfully captured the initiation and evolution of distinct damage modes within individual tows. Overall, this research establishes a foundation for meso-scale modelling strategies that can accurately predict both mechanical behaviour and failure mechanisms in meso-architected laminates, an essential step toward the design of next-generation composite structures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the following funding:

ARC LIEF: Australasian facility for the automated fabrication of high-performance bespoke components (LE140100082).

ARC ITTC: ARC Training Centre for Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites (IC160100040).

ACM CRC: Australian Composites Manufacturing Cooperative Research Centre (ACM CRC) (CRCXXIIIA000003).

The authors further acknowledge the Tyree X-ray CT Facility, X-ray Analysis Facility, Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre, UNSW Sydney, for the acquisition of the 3D μ XCT images.

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